

Research Article

Simultaneous determination of mesalazine and rifaximin in synthetic mixture using spectrophotometric technique (simultaneous equation method)

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ABSTRACT

Objective: A simple, accurate and precise spectroscopic method was developed for simultaneous estimation of Mesalazine and Rifaximin in synthetic mixture using Simultaneous Equation Method. Objective of the study was to deliver information related to Mesalazine and Rifaximin combination's analytical method.

Methods: The absorbance was measured at 328 nm for Mesalazine and 292 nm for Rifaximin and calibration curves were plotted as absorbance versus concentration, respectively. The method was found to be linear ($r^2 > 0.999$) in the range of 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Mesalazine at 328 nm. The linear correlation was obtained ($r^2 > 0.999$) in the range of 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Rifaximin at 292 nm.

Results: The limit of determination (LOD) was 0.215 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.214 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Mesalazine and Rifaximin respectively. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was 0.652 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.648 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Mesalazine and Rifaximin respectively. The accuracy of this method was evaluated by recovery studies and good recovery results were obtained greater than 99%. The method was successfully applied for simultaneous determination of Mesalazine and Rifaximin in binary mixture.

Conclusions: The method was successfully applied to pharmaceutical synthetic mixture which is considered in approved patent which show no interference. The result of analysis has been validated statistically and by recovery studies. So this method accurate, precise, robust, rugged and economic in nature.

Keywords: Mesalazine, Rifaximin, Simultaneous estimation, Simultaneous equation method

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Introduction

Mesalazine and Rifaximin use for Inflammatory Bowel Disease. Mesalazine is used as in anti-

inflammatory agent, Steroidal. Rifaximin is used in gastrointestinal agents, anti-infective agent. The use of Rifaximin in combination with Mesalazine has been proved to provide beneficial effect in inflammatory bowel disease.

The mechanism of Mesalazine and Rifaximin is quite different. Mesalazine and Rifaximin are two different types of drugs offering some symptomatic relief to the IBD patients. Mesalazine treats inflammation, whereas, Rifaximin reduces bio burden. Mesalazine and Rifaximin novel combination used in treatment of inflammatory bowel disease patented by Lupin Ltd, WIPO WO2009047801 A₁.¹

Mesalazine

Mesalazine is a salicylate, its therapeutic effect does not appear to be related to cyclooxygenase inhibition; indeed, traditional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs actually may exacerbate inflammatory bowel disease. Although the mechanism of action of mesalazine is not fully understood, it appears to be topical rather than systemic. Mucosal production of Arachidonic acid metabolites, both through the cyclooxygenase pathways, i.e., prostanoids, and through the lipoxygenase pathways, i.e., leukotrienes and hydroxyecosatetraenoic acids, is increased in patients with chronic inflammatory bowel disease, and it is possible that mesalazine diminishes inflammation by blocking cyclooxygenase and inhibiting prostaglandin production in the colon. Mesalazine appears to diminish inflammation by inhibiting cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase, thereby decreasing the production of prostaglandins, and leukotrienes and hydroxyecosatetraenoic acids (HETs) respectively. It is also believed acts as a scavenger of oxygen-derived free radicals, which are produced in greater in patients with IBD.²

Figure 1: Chemical structure of mesalazine.

Mesalazine is chemically 5-Amino-2-Hydroxybenzoic acid. It appears as off white to gray, having molecular weight 153.14 g/mol.³⁻⁵

Rifaximin

Rifaximin is a semisynthetic, rifamycin-based non-systemic antibiotic, meaning that the drug will not pass the gastrointestinal wall into the circulation as is common for other types of orally administered antibiotics. It is used to treat diarrhea caused by *E. coli*. Rifaximin acts by inhibiting RNA synthesis in susceptible bacteria by binding to the beta-subunit of bacterial deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA)-dependent ribonucleic acid (RNA) polymerase enzyme. This results in the blockage of the translocation step that normally follows the formation of the first phosphodiester bond, which occurs in the transcription process.⁶

Rifaximin is chemically (7S,9E,11S,12R,13S,14R,15R,16R,17S,18S,19,21Z)-2,15,17,36-tetrahydroxy-11-methoxy-3,7,12,14,16,18,22,30-octamethyl-6,23-dioxo-8,37-dioxo-24,27,33-triazahexacyclo[23.10.1.1^{4,7}.0^{5,35}.0^{26,34}.0^{27,32}]heptatriaconta-1,3,5(35),9,19,21,25(36),26(34),28,30,32-undecaen-13-yl acetate. It is a Red Orange Crystalline Powder having molecular weight 785.87 g/mol.^{7,8}

Figure 2: Chemical structure of rifaximin.

The review of literature regarding quantitative analysis of Mesalazine and Rifaximin revealed that no Simultaneous Equation method attempt was made to develop analytical methods for Mesalazine and Rifaximin. Some spectrometric methods and chromatographic methods have been reported for the estimation of the individual

and combination of drugs. The focus of the present study was to develop and validate a rapid, stable, specific, and economic Spectroscopic method for the estimation of Mesalazine and Rifaximin in Synthetic Mixture.

Theory⁹

We can find out concentration of both the drug from combination mixture using the simultaneous equation method. In this method using the absorbance of both the drug and mixture at their wavelength and put this value in following equation and we can find out the concentration of drugs present in combination.

$$Cx = \frac{(A_2 \times Ay_1) - (A_1 \times Ay_2)}{(Ay_1 \times Ax_2) - (Ay_2 \times Ax_1)} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$Cy = \frac{(A_1 \times Ax_2) - (A_2 \times Ax_1)}{(Ax_2 \times Ay_1) - (Ax_1 \times Ay_2)} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where, Cx = Concentration of drug A

Cy = Concentration of drug B

A₁ = Absorbance of mixture at wavelength 1

A₂ = Absorbance of mixture at wavelength 2

Ax₁ = Absorptivity of drug A at wavelength 1

Ax₂ = Absorptivity of drug A at wavelength 2

Ay₁ = Absorptivity of drug B at wavelength 1

Ay₂ = Absorptivity of drug B at wavelength 2

Materials and Methods

Apparatus

A double beam UV/Visible spectro-photometer (Shimadzu model 2450, Japan) with spectral width of 2 nm, 1 cm quartz cells was used to measure absorbance of all the solutions. Spectra were automatically obtained by UV-Probe system software, an analytical balance (Sartorius CD2250, Gottingen, Germany) was used for weighing the samples, Sonicator (D120/2H, TRANS-O-SONIC), Class 'B' volumetric glasswares were used (Borosilicte). All instruments and glass wares were calibrated.

Reference samples

MESA and RIFA reference standard are kindly supply by CTX Life Sci. Sachin, Surat and

Lupin LTD, Ankleshwar as a gift sample respectively.

Materials and reagents

Methanol AR Grade (FINAR), Distilled Water, NaOH AR Grade (RANCHEM), Distilled water, HCl (ASTRON) was used for development purpose.

Preparation of standard solution and synthetic mixture

Preparation of stock solution of Pravastatin

An accurately weighed quantity equivalent to 10 mg of Mesalazine was transferred to 100 ml volumetric and dissolved and diluted to the mark with the 0.01 N NaOH to obtain standard solution having concentration of MESA (100 µg/ml).

Preparation of standard stock solution of Valsartan

An accurately weighed quantity equivalent to 10 mg of Rifaximin was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved and diluted to the mark with 0.01 N NaOH to obtain standard solution having concentration of RIFA (100 µg/ml).

Preparation of standard mixture solution (MESA+ RIFA)

4.0 ml of working standard stock solution of MESA (100 µg/ml) and 1.0 ml of standard Stock solution of RIFA (100 µg/ml) were pipetted out into 10ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted to the mark with 0.01 N NaOH to get 40 µg/ml of MESA and 10 µg/ml of RIFA.

Preparation of test solution

Table 1: The preparation of synthetic mixture was as per patent.

Ingredients	Quantity (mg)
Mesalazine	800
Rifaximin	200
Na.CMC	544
MCC	416
Mg. Stearate	q. s.
	Total=2000 mg

From that powder equivalent to 100 mg of synthetic mixture in 100 ml volume flask dissolve in 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH. Sonicate for 15 min diluent up to the 100 ml with 0.01 N NaOH and shake vigorously filter the solution. Filter the solution & further dilute. Withdraw 0.1 ml and make up to 10 ml that give 40 ppm and 10ppm of MESA and RIFA respectively.

Results and Discussion

Selection of wavelength for estimation of Mesalazine and Rifaximin

The Standard Stock Solutions of Mesalazine and Rifaximin were scanned in the range of 200 to 400nm against 0.01 N NaOH as a blank. Maximum absorbance was obtained at 328 nm and 292nm for Mesalazine and Rifaximin, respectively. But Spectra were no overlay.

Figure 3: Overlain zero order spectra of MESA and RIFA in 4:1 ratios, respectively with the combination solution (4:1).

Figure 4: Overlain zero order Spectra of MESA and RIFA (1:1) ratio, respectively.

Validation parameters¹⁰

Linearity

Five point calibration curves were obtained in the concentration range of 10-50 µg/ml for Mesalazine and 10-50 µg/ml for Rifaximin. The response of drug was found to be linear in investigation range and the regression equations was found to be $y = 0.0199x - 0.0008$ for MESA (n=5) and $y = 0.0178x + 0.0367$ for RIFA (n=5), with the correlation coefficient 0.9992 and 0.9991 (n=5) respectively, is listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Calibration data for MESA and RIFA at 328 nm and 292 nm, respectively.

Conc. (µg/ml)	MESA at 328 nm (n=6)		RIFA at 292 nm (n=6)	
	Abs ±SD	%RSD	Abs ±SD	%RSD
10	0.189±0.0018	0.992	0.142±0.0013	0.964
20	0.399±0.0032	0.820	0.316±0.0025	0.816
30	0.608±0.0046	0.769	0.509±0.0024	0.477
40	0.795±0.0021	0.269	0.665±0.0051	0.769
50	0.982±0.0090	0.921	0.859±0.0058	0.678

Calibration curves for MESA

This series consisted of five concentrations of standard MESA solution ranging from 10 to 50 µg/ml. The solutions were prepared by pipetting out Standard MESA stock solution (100 µg/ml). Then pipetting out (1.0 ml, 2.0 ml, 3.0 ml, 4.0 ml, and 5.0 ml) was transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH. A zero order spectrum of the resulting solution was recorded, measured the absorbance at 328 nm against a reagent blank solution (0.01 N NaOH). Calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance versus respective concentration of MESA.

Calibration curve for RIFA

This series consisted of five concentrations of standard RIFA solution ranging from 10 to 50 µg/ml. The solutions were prepared by pipetting out Standard RIFA stock solution (1.0 ml, 2.0

ml, 3.0 ml, 4.0ml and 5.0 ml) was transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH. A zero order spectrum of the resulting solution was recorded, measured the absorbance at 292 nm against a reagent blank solution (0.01 N NaOH). Calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance versus respective concentration of RIFA.

Figure 5: Calibration curve for MESA at 328 nm.

Figure 6: Calibration curve for RIFA at 292 nm.

Precision

The precision of the method was evaluated in terms of inter-day and intra-day by carrying out independent assays of three concentrations chosen from range of the standard curves (10, 30, and 50 µg/ml of MESA and 10, 30, 50 µg/ml of RIFA) and the %RSD of assay (inter-day and

intra-day) was calculated. The results of study are shown in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3: Intraday precision data for estimation of MESA and RIFA. *(n=3)

Conc. (µg/ml)	At 328 nm		At 292 nm	
	Mean	%RSD	Mean	%RSD
MESA+ RIFA				
10:10	0.190	0.802	0.143	0.694
30:30	0.613	0.163	0.515	0.194
50:50	0.994	0.153	0.865	0.115

Table 4: Interday precision data for estimation of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Conc. (µg/ml)	At 328nm		At 292nm	
	Mean	%RSD	Mean	%RSD
MESA+ RIFA				
10:10	0.191	0.523	0.144	0.694
30:30	0.615	0.248	0.514	0.298
50:50	0.995	0.100	0.864	0.115

Accuracy

Composition of synthetic mixture

Table 5: Total amount of API.

Amt. of API in synthetic mixture (mg)		Amt. of API Spiking (mg)		Total Amt. (mg)	
MESA	RIFA	MESA	RIFA	MESA	RIFA
40	10	-	-	40	10
40	10	32	8	72	18
40	10	40	10	80	20
40	10	48	12	88	22

From the synthesis mixture weighs accurately equivalent about 100 mg of RIFA. Take Four 100ml Volumetric Flask and in each flask add synthetic mixture equivalent to 10 mg of RIFA. Flask 1 form as a Placebo and remaining flask 2, 3, 4 spike with 80, 100, 120% of solid API. Repeat the same procedure for MESA as per

Table. Take content in 100 ml volumetric flask dissolved in 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH and Sonicate for 15 min make up the volume with 0.01 N NaOH up to 100 ml. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. With the Mesalazine & Rifaximin with the ratio

detection (LOD) were found to be 0.215 µg/ml for MESA and 0.214 µg/ml for RIFA and respectively and limit of quantitation (LOQ) were found to be 0.652 µg/ml for MESA and 0.648 µg/ml for RIFA presented in Table 7.

Table 6: Recovery data of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Level of recovery	Total Conc. (µg/ml)		Result of recovery study					
	MES	RIFA	Total Quantity Found (µg/ml)		% Recovery ± %RSD			
			MESA	RIFA	MESA		RIFA	
0%	20	5	20.09	5.02	100.4	0.174	100.5	0.304
80 %	36	9	36.08	9.00	100.5	0.164	100.2	0.381
100 %	40	10	39.98	10.01	99.92	0.202	100.3	0.502
120 %	44	11	43.97	11.01	99.90	0.061	100.1	0.255
Mean of 3 Determination					100.2	0.314	100.3	0.170

4:1 dissolved in 0.01 N NaOH with small volume of Solvent, Sonicate for 15 mins, then make up to 100 ml with 0.01 N NaOH with all excipients. Now, this solution was used for further dilution.

Take total amt. of formulation in 100 ml of volumetric flask and add 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH, Sonicate, filter it; make up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH. From it 0.5 ml Dilute to 10 ml with 0.01 N NaOH of 0%, 80%, 100% and 120% solution this Accuracy method done by spiking method. Data from nine determinations over three concentration levels covering the specified range was determined and % recovery was calculated. The % recovery values are tabulated in Table 6. The value of %RSD within the limit indicated that the method is accurate and percentage recovery shows that there is no interference from the excipients.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) of the method were evaluated by standard deviation of response and slope method. LOQ and LOD were calculated by the equation $LOD = 3.3 \times N/B$ and $LOQ = 10 \times N/B$, where “N” is standard deviation of the absorbance, and “B” is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve. The limit of

Table 7: LOD and LOQ data of MESA and RIFA *(n=10).

Conc. (µg/ml)		Avg. abs % ±SD	RSD	Avg. abs*±SD	% RSD
MES A	RIF A	(328.00n m) MESA		(292.00n m) RIFA RFC	
20	20	0.403 ± 0.001	0.31 ± 3	0.318 ± 0.001	0.36 ± 3
LOD (µg/ml)		0.215		0.214	
LOQ (µg/ml)		0.652		0.648	

Robustness and ruggedness

Robustness was done by different instrument and difference in preparation of stock solution. The result was decided by %RSD which is in the limit which is mentioned in Table 8.

From the prepared powder equivalent to 100 mg of synthetic mixture in 100 ml volume flask dissolve in 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH. Sonicate for 15 min diluent up to the 100 ml with 0.01 N NaOH and Shake Vigorously filter the solution & Filter the solution & further dilute. Withdraw 0.1 ml

Table 8: Robustness and Ruggedness data of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Parameters		At 328nm (MESA+RIFA)		At 292nm (MESA+RIFA)	
		Abs	%RSD	Abs	%RSD
ROBUSTNESS					
Different instrument	Inst.1	0.404	0.377	0.319	0.475
	Inst.2	0.405	0.376	0.321	0.623
Different Analyst	Analyst 1	0.407	0.375	0.320	0.476
	Analyst 2	0.406	0.490	0.322	0.473
RUGGEDNESS					
Change wavelength	326& 290 nm	0.391	0.511	0.306	0.498
	330& 294 nm	0.414	0.368	0.318	0.314
Change Ratio	1:1	0.404	0.377	0.319	0.478
	4:1	0.796	0.227	0.144	0.694
	1:4	0.191	1.087	0.672	0.227
Solvent change	0.012N NaOH	0.475	0.295	0.353	0.458
	0.009N NaOH	0.312	0.309	0.295	0.242

Table 9: Analysis data of synthetic mixture *(n=3).

Sr. No.	Formulation (synthetic mixture)		Absorbance* (328.00nm) MESA	% Assay MESA ±SD	Absorbance* (250.00nm) RIFA	% Assay RIFA ±SD
	MES	RIFA				
1			0.909	100.93	0.426	101.70
2	40	10	0.911	± 0.05	0.425	± 0.20
3			0.908		0.427	

and make up to 10 ml that gives 40 µg/ml of MESA and 10 µg/ml of RIFA were recorded and the absorbance at 328 nm and 292 nm were noted for estimation of MESA and RIFA, respectively. The concentration of MESA and RIFA in mixture was determined using the corresponding calibration graph. The percent assay shows that there is no interference from excipients and the proposed method can successfully applied to analysis of commercial formulation containing MESA and RIFA. The % assay values are tabulated in Table 9.

A new, Simultaneous Equation method has been developed for estimation of Mesalazine and Rifaximin. The method was validated by employment of ICH guidelines.¹⁰ The validation data is indicative of good precision and accuracy, and prove the reliability of the method. The method involves the generation of

absorbance spectra followed by measurement of the absorbance.

Conclusions

The proposed method does not require any sophisticated mathematical treatment for the absorption data, and it exhibits several advantages over other Spectrophotometric methods for resolution of binary mixtures. Therefore, the presented methodology is adequate for the routine quality control analysis of these fixed-dose combinations.

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Table 10: Summary of validation parameters.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Mesalazine	Rifaximin
1	Wave length Max.	328.00nm	292.00nm
2	Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (n=6)	10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Regression equation	$y = 0.0199x - 0.0008$	$y = 0.0178x + 0.0367$
4	Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9992	0.9991
5	Accuracy (%Recovery) (n=3)	100.2%	100.3%
6	Precision		
	Intra-day (%RSD)(n=3)	0.153-0.802	0.115-0.699
	Inter-day (%RSD)(n=3)	0.100-0.523	0.115-0.694
7	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (n=10)	0.215	0.214
8	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (n=10)	0.652	0.648
9	Robustness (%RSD)(n=3)		
	Change in instrument	0.376-0.377	0.475-0.623
	Change in Analyst	0.375-0.490	0.473-0.476
10	Ruggedness (%RSD)(n=3)	0.295-0.309	0.242-0.458
	Change Solvent	0.368-0.511	0.314-0.498
	Change in Wavelength		
11	Assay	100.93	101.70

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